

EARTH SCIENCES

INTEGRATED LAND RESOURCES MANAGEMENT BASED ON A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF SOIL AND BOTTOM SEDIMENTS POLLUTION (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE UKRAINIAN DANUBE REGION)

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Abstract

The study is devoted to the development of measures for integrated land resource management in the region, taking into account a comprehensive assessment of the state of soil and bottom sediment contamination in water bodies in the Ukrainian Danube region. The study used methods of analysis and generalization of monitoring data of research objects, comparative comparison, logical generalization and analogies in combination with expert assessments, monographic and graph-analytical studies. The results are presented on the basis of field and laboratory studies. The state of land resources of the Danube region of Ukraine is determined to be "unsatisfactory". The risk of soil ecosystem disturbance for most of the region is assessed as "increased". The results of monitoring in storage areas of unsuitable chemical plant protection products indicate an excess of maximum permissible concentrations of individual pollutants by 5.0-32.0 times. The ecological state of soils is assessed as "medium" - "severe" with risks at the level of "significant" - "high". In general, the ecological state of the bottom sediments of the water bodies of the Danube region of Ukraine is assessed as "satisfactory". In order to develop sustainable land use plans, a comprehensive assessment of the stability of the soil ecosystem and a risk assessment during the storage of unsuitable chemical plant protection products were carried out. Recommendations were proposed for the use of indicators of the ecological state, taking into account the criteria of physical degradation and soil pollution. The results obtained can be aimed at forming a regional strategy for effective and sustainable land use based on tools and mechanisms aimed at solving problems of socio-economic development, taking into account the likely impact of destabilizing factors.

Keywords: ukrainian danube region, sustainable land use, ecological risk.

Introduction. Systemic and very negative anthropogenic processes that have occurred over the past decades, as well as misconceptions about the inexhaustibility and unlimited possibilities of ecosystems for self-purification, have led to significant disruptions in the development of economic and ecological systems. That is why scientists have recognized the need to ensure the livelihoods of the population of the regions of Ukraine only if the consequences of economic activity are taken into account when assessing the capabilities of our future generations to meet their needs [9].

The main national wealth of Ukraine is land resources with its fertile soils, the quality level of which is one of the highest in Europe, and the amount of arable land per person in Ukraine exceeds the similar indicator in the countries of the European Union by an average of more than 2.5 times [19].

According to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, in 2018-2020, the area of agricultural land in

our country was 41,489.3 thousand hectares and accounted for 68.7% of the total area of the state [11]. In terms of the volume of agricultural land per capita, Ukraine has an indicator of 0.93 hectares and ranks fourth among other countries in the world after Canada (1.73 hectares), Russia (1.51 hectares), and the USA (1.26 hectares). In terms of the volume of arable land per capita, Ukraine, with an indicator of 0.74 hectares, ranks second after Canada (1.25 hectares) [10]. Considering also that Ukraine has a significant part (3%) of the world reserves of black soil and other most fertile types of soil, it can be stated that Ukraine occupies one of the leading positions in the world in terms of quantity and quality of land resources. However, despite the high land and resource potential, the return on 1 hectare of agricultural land in Ukraine is 270–320 euro, and in the EU countries this figure exceeds 2000 euro [5,11].

Literature review. The scientific and methodological foundations of the economic and ecological as-

assessment of the interaction of society and the environment, including for the territory of Ukraine, have been studied by a number of scientists [1,3,9]. Special attention in these studies was paid to the analysis and assessment of land and water resources - the basic natural factors that determine both the level of development of the production sphere of the regions and the social component of life [7]. Considerable attention was also paid to the theoretical and methodological principles of optimizing integrated management from the point of view of ensuring resource and environmental security.

The land potential of each region is the basis of its economic development and socio-ecological well-being. At the same time, the degree of development and economic load on the vast majority of the territory of Ukraine have already reached levels that exceed the ability to self-renew.

Among the main directions of solving the above-mentioned problems, the following can be distinguished:

- development of conceptual foundations of economic and ecological assessment of land potential from the point of view of safe and sustainable development [3,9];
- determination of indicators of ecological safety as characteristics of the level of protection from negative impact, taking into account the achievement of the goals of sustainable development of the socio-economic and ecological system [7];
- probability of factors and consequences of events and levels of damage in the theory of ecological risk assessment [8].

The topics of integrated land resources management from the point of view of ecological safety are devoted to the works of many Ukrainian and foreign scientists. For example, anthropogenic impacts are studied in the works of Earl K. Ellis [13], various ecological and managerial aspects in the field of land use are devoted to the works of J. Scott [11], R. Rosytsky [5,19]. J. Thunen in his work "Isolated State" studies the concept of land rent, the impact of taxes on agriculture, and the land rent tax. Theoretical and methodological aspects of land management in independent Ukraine have been studied by many scientists, in particular Bystryakov I.K., Tretyak A.M., who substantiated the principles and individual methods of land management [19].

R.M. Kuryltsiv R.M., Kovalenko P.I., Petrochenko O.V., Prodanchuk M.A. and others. consider various aspects of integrated land use management, including the justification of its methodology and basic algorithms [5,10,11,19].

A number of both foreign and domestic scientists consider the issue of regional integrated land use management from the point of view of environmental safety through the assessment of the probability of environmental risks of land resource pollution [1,18,20,21]. First of all, this concerns the assessment of risks of technological origin, especially when introducing new technologies. In this case, it is proposed to use a probabilistic safety analysis apparatus based on hazard modeling and a scenario approach [21].

Unsolved aspects of the problem. It should be noted that despite the significant volume of publications on environmental risk assessment studies, there are still questions for the scientific search for modern comprehensive approaches to ensuring regional resource and environmental security. In addition, environmental risk assessment is significantly limited by the lack of data on the impact on land resources as risk objects in terms of assessing consequences. This necessitates the need to provide a systematic approach to collecting this data and modeling the assessment of the safety of the functioning of regional ecological systems. Such an approach is extremely important, since the main goal of risk assessment is to translate complex and specific scientific information to persons who must make effective management decisions.

The relevance of assessing the risk of contamination of soils and bottom sediments of water bodies in the Ukrainian Danube region is associated with the following issues:

- the uniqueness of the Danube region within the Odessa region of Ukraine in terms of geographical location, environment and prospects for economic development, as a direction of European integration processes (Fig. 1);
- the need to assess environmental risks in connection with increased requirements of environmental legislation and as a preventive measure in the event of likely significant economic losses in the future;

Fig. 1. Scheme of the Danube River Basin and the Ukrainian Danube Region

– lack of study of possible environmental risk scenarios for this region in the context of growing anthropogenic impact on natural ecosystems;

– lack of a developed comprehensive strategy for effective and sustainable management of natural resources based on regional risk assessment, aimed at solving problems between the goals of socio-economic development and the negative consequences of the impact of destabilizing factors.

Purpose.

The aim of the work was to assess the environmental risks of soil contamination in the storage areas of unsuitable chemical plant protection products and bottom sediments in the Ukrainian section of the Danube River and the lakes of the region. To do this, it was necessary to solve the following tasks:

1. To conduct an analysis of methods for assessing the environmental risks of soil and bottom sediment contamination.
2. To develop recommendations for the use of indicator indicators of soil condition taking into account the criterion of their physical degradation and contamination.
3. To assess the general condition of land resources in the Danube regions of Ukraine and to assess the risk of disrupting the stability of soil ecosystems.
4. To assess the environmental risks when handling unsuitable chemical plant protection products.
5. To assess the condition and environmental risks of bottom sediment contamination in water bodies of the Danube region of Ukraine.

Methods. To solve the tasks set in the work, based on data from field ecological monitoring of the territory, in which the authors of the work directly participated [4,15], methods of analysis and synthesis of the obtained results, comparative comparison, logical generalization and analogies were used, in combination with expert assessments, monographic and graph-analytical studies. Taking this into account, a comprehensive assessment of the ecological state of soils and bottom sediments of the Danube region of Ukraine and determination of the risks of their pollution were carried

out using the methods proposed in the works [12,22]. It should be noted that the results obtained allow for specific management decisions to be made regarding the mitigation of the negative impact on land resources and the priority of the implementation of environmental protection measures.

When assessing the risk of soil contamination in the Danube region of Ukraine, the following were taken into account:

- 1) the current state of agricultural lands with the determination of indicators of the structure of land and soil cover, the ecological sustainability of land resources, the content of humus and basic plant nutrients, the yield of main crops, the existing degree of erosion and salinity, as well as the score (quality) of the lands;
- 2) the state of the forest fund lands according to the indicators of the structure of forest lands, forest cover, forest quality, completeness of plantings, stocks of forest-forming species, average wood growth;
- 3) the current state of the lands of the nature reserve fund (NRF) according to the indicators of the structure of the NRF lands, the number and location of existing NRF objects by territorial taxa and the percentage of NRF lands in the structure of the lands of the corresponding taxon.

Integral indicators of the state of land resources (I_{z_st}) were determined as the average score of all indicators:

$$I_{z_st} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k Z_i, \quad (1)$$

where Z_i - is the score of the i -th indicator; k - is the number of indicators.

Depending on the obtained calculation results, each indicator was assigned a corresponding score (I_i): 1 - favorable condition; 2 - satisfactory; 3 - mediocre, 4 - severe; 5 - very severe.

The integral indicator of land resource pollution (I_{zab}) was calculated using the formula

$$I_{zab} = \max(I_1, I_2, \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=3}^6 I_i, I_7, \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=8}^{10} I_i), \quad (2)$$

where I_i - is the score of the i -th indicator.

Soil resistance to pollution depends on many factors, the main of which are: slope steepness, stoniness, resistivity, structure, mechanical composition of the soil, type of water regime, humus content, etc. Depending on the value of the territory factor, the score of the territorial taxon indicator was determined. At the final stage, a comprehensive ecological assessment of soil resistance (C , %) was determined using the formula shown below:

$$C = \frac{100}{Q} \sum_{j=1}^N C_j, \quad (3)$$

where C_j - is the score for the j -th evaluation indicator; N - is the number of indicators of the calculation scheme by which the evaluation is carried out; Q - is the maximum possible sum of points for the indicators by which the calculation was carried out ($Q = 4N$) according to the indicators.

Як індикаторний показник обігу промислових відходів та їх накопичення, запропонований показник зведеної щільності утворення промислових відходів за рік (Z_w , т/км²), який розраховувався за формулою

As an indicator of industrial waste circulation and its accumulation, the indicator of the aggregate density of industrial waste generation per year (Z_w , т/км²) was proposed, which was calculated by the formula

$$Z_w = \frac{\Pi_{zuv}}{S}, \quad (4)$$

where Π_{zuv} - is a complex indicator of total waste generation/accumulation, т/year; S - is the area of the corresponding territorial taxon, км².

В свою чергу Π_{zuv} визначався за формулою

In turn, Π_{zuv} was determined by the formula

$$\Pi_{zuv} = 5000M_1 + 500M_2 + 50M_3 + M_4, \quad (5)$$

where M_1, M_2, M_3 та M_4 - the amount of generated (accumulated) industrial waste of the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th hazard classes, т/year.

Indicators of the ecological state of soils are: the area of land withdrawn from agricultural use due to its degradation, covering of the humus layer with abiotic sediments, increasing soil density, increasing groundwater levels, humus losses over the past 10 years. Also taken into account are: an increase in the content of easily soluble salts and the share of exchangeable sodium in the soil, a decrease in the level of active microbial mass, exceeding the MPC of chemical substances, the share of contaminated agricultural products, and a decrease in average yield [4].

The integral indicator of the ecological state of soils (I_{Gr_st}) was determined by the maximum score of the worst indicator:

$$I_{Gr_st} = \max(I_1, I_2, \dots, I_j, I_k), \quad (6)$$

where I_j - score of the j -th indicator; k - number of indicators.

Taking into account the adopted approach of comprehensive assessment of land condition, the regional assessment of environmental risk in the current state of the i -th environmental component was performed according to the formula [12]

$$P_i^c = f_i(K_i^c, H_i^c), \quad (7)$$

where P_i^c - probability of soil stability disturbance at the current state of the i -th ecosystem components; K_i^c - current state of the i -th environmental component; H_i^c - level of anthropogenic load from the impact of negative factors on the i -th environmental component.

The ecological risk for soils (P_s^c) was determined by the formula

$$P_s^c = f(S_d \langle d = \overline{1, N_S} \rangle, H_{SI} \langle l = \overline{1, N_{HS}} \rangle), \quad (8)$$

where S_d - is the current state of soils; H_{SI} - is an integral assessment of the level of anthropogenic load from the impact of negative factors on soils according to the d -th indicator.

For a more detailed assessment of environmental risk, it is necessary to take into account the ability of the regional ecosystem of land resources to self-recovery, the distance of ecosystems from sources of influence, the duration of the effects of anthropogenic load factors, etc. Then the risk of disruption of the stability of the i -th component of the ecosystem (P_i) is expressed as a function of the type

$$P_i = f(r, K_i^K, H_i, L, t), \quad (9)$$

where K_i^K - is the critical state of the i -th component of the ecosystem; r - is the distance of the ecosystem from the sources of influence; t - is the time for the ecosystem to reach the critical state; L - is the ability of the ecosystem to self-recover from the negative impact of anthropogenic load H_i .

Results. The development of agricultural lands and the plowing of the territories of the Danube districts of the Odessa region (Tatarbunarsky, Artsyzsky, Reniysky, Izmailsky and Kiliya districts) are characterized on average by the following indicators: 66.2% - the level of development of agricultural lands; 87.0% - plowing of territories [4].

It was established that the integral indicator of the assessment of the state of land resources I_{z_st} of the Danube districts of the Odessa region (Table 1) varies from 3.00 to 3.17 and corresponds to the II group of objects ($3.0 < I_{z_st} < 3.3$), in which the condition of the soils is assessed as "unsatisfactory".

From an ecological point of view, the land resources of the Danube region of Ukraine should be considered as reclaimed agricultural landscapes that have been exploited for more than one century. The current state of land resource use does not meet the requirements of rational environmental management, primarily due to the violation of the ratio of arable land area to natural forage lands, which negatively affects the sustainability of the agricultural landscape. Agricultural land development exceeds the ecologically permissible norm and in recent years it has only increased.

The main problem of the deterioration of the condition of the lands of the Ukrainian Danube region, as well as the Odessa region as a whole, remains soil degradation, primarily the development of erosion processes and physical soil degradation.

According to expert assessment, physical degradation of land resources is manifested, first of all, in the compaction of almost 38.4% of the arable land area of

the region, and the area of all degraded lands reaches 98 thousand hectares. Erosion, as a factor of soil cover degradation and ecological hazard, is estimated, first of all, by the intensity of washing out and the volumes of movement of the soil substrate and is from 10-15 to 20-25 t/ha. One of the reasons for the deterioration of the ecological condition of the lands in the region is flooding and landslides, which have become more active in recent years. In general, in the region, the total area of flooding in some years reached 20.6 thousand ha, and the total damage reaches almost 62% of the territory [4].

Calculations of the risk assessment of soil ecosystem stability for the Artsyz, Kiliya and Tatarbunar districts showed a “minimum” level ($P_s^c=0.20$), and for the Izmail and Reniy districts – “increased” ($P_s^c=0.25$).

To assess the environmental risks of handling unsuitable chemical plant protection products (NCPP), it was determined that there are 6 NCPP warehouses located in the Danube regions, or 1.08% of the total number of such facilities in the Odessa region, and the amount of NCPP stored there is 27.8 tons, or 2.1% of the total volume in the warehouses of the region [15]. All of these warehouses are not certified and are in unsatisfactory condition. The assessment of soil contamination was carried out by comparing the measured/

Soil contamination was assessed by comparing measured concentrations of pollutants (cadmium, copper, zinc, manganese, cobalt, total iron, nickel, arsenic, lead, mercury, DDT, DDE, DDD, γ -HCHH/lindane, heptachlor) with the MPCs established in Ukraine [13] and sanitary standards [20].

Table 1

Assessment of the lands condition in the Danube areas of Odesa region [14]

Administrative-territorial entity*	Ecological condition indicators						Integrated index of condition	Group acc. to the integrated index $I_{z=0}$
	ploughness	humus content	ecological resistance	forest cover	erosional feature	reserves		
Artsyz district	3	3	3	2	4	4	3.17	II
Kiliya district	4	3	3	2	4	2	3.00	II
Izmail district	4	3	2	2	4	4	3.00	II
Reni district	3	3	3	2	4	4	3.17	II
Tatarbunar district	4	3	3	2	4	2	3.00	II
Danube districts in whole	4	3	3	2	4	3	3.17	II
Odesa region in whole	3	3	2	3	4	4	3.17	II

* Remarks: administrative-territorial units of districts of Odessa region are listed before the implementation of the 2020 administrative reform

Data from 645 analyses were used to assess soil contamination. According to the results of the studies, exceedances of 1.05 to 32.0 MPC for the following pollutants were established: copper (2.3% of the total number of samples); lead (4.6%); zinc (9.3%); DDT (11.6%); DDE (9.3%); DDD (2.3%).

The most dangerous situation is observed near the following storage facilities for NHCZR:

- in the village of Shevchenkove, Kiliya district, where all soil samples exceeded the MPC for zinc (by 1.05-1.26 times), and in one sample for lead (by 1.20 times), DDT and DDE (by 1.80-2.20 times);
- in the village of Zadunaivka, Artsyz district, where 50% of samples exceeded the MPC for DDT (by 2.10-32.0 times), DDE (by 1.01-22.0 times), and DDD (by 5.00 times).

Assessment of the ecological state and calculations of the level of ecological risk of soils in the locations of the NHZZR storage warehouses showed the following:

1) near the village of Desantne and the village of Stari Troyany in the Kiliya district, the village of Utkonosivka and the village of Novokalanchak in the Izmail district, the ecological state of the soils is determined as “satisfactory”, and the level of ecological risk is “increased” ($P_s^c=0.25-0.30$);

2) near the village of Novoselivka and the village of Vasylivka in the Kiliya district, the village of Kyrnichky in the Izmail district, the village of Ostrovne, the village of Glavani, the village of Kamianske and between the villages of Delen and Novoselivka in the Artsyz district, the ecological state of the soils is determined as “medium”, and the level of ecological risk is “significant” » ($P_s^c=0.35-0.40$);

3) near the village of Shevchenkove in the Kiliya district and the village of In Zadunaivka, Artsyz district, the ecological condition of soils is defined as “severe”, and the level of ecological risk is “high” ($P_s^c=0.60-0.65$).

The assessment of the ecological risk of bottom sediment pollution of water bodies of the Ukrainian Danube region was carried out in the area between the city of Reni and the mouth of the Danube, as well as in the Danube lakes. The assessment of bottom sediment pollution was carried out based on the data of sample analyses from 27 monitoring points [4,15]. The list of pollutants is similar to that used to assess soil pollution. The assessment of bottom sediment pollution was carried out based on the data of 390 analyses.

According to the results of the conducted studies

(Table 2), the following pollutants were found to exceed the MPC by 1.2-4.95:

– copper (3.3% of all samples, with 9.2% exceeding the MPC registered in sections of the Danube River and only 0.8% in Lake Yalpug in the section of the Bolgrad water intake, the MPC was exceeded by 1.07-2.70 times);

– zinc (1.5% of all samples from Lake Yalpug, MPC exceeded 1.55-1.57 times);

– manganese (3.1% of all samples from the Danube River, MPC exceeded 1.15-1.70 times);

– lead (2.3% of all samples, MPC exceeded 1.65-4.95 times);

– nickel (3.1% of all samples, MPC exceeded 1.25-1.40 times).

In the bottom sediments of the Danube and in the Danube lakes, the residual amount of chemical plant protection products (DDT, DDE, DDD, γ -HCTC/lindane, heptachlor) in the studied samples was not established.

Spatial analysis of the indicators of bottom sediment pollution in the Ukrainian section of the Danube River shows that the greatest pollution is observed in

the transborder section near the city of Reni, where the maximum permissible concentration for lead (1.70-4.95 times) and copper (2.30-2.70 times) is recorded.

In the section of the river near the city of Izmail, the quality indicators of bottom sediments generally correspond to the established maximum permissible concentration, however, for copper, the contamination of bottom soils is 1.25-1.50 maximum permissible concentration.

On the section of the river near the city of Kiliya, a deterioration in the quality of bottom sediments is again observed: for copper - up to 2.70 MPC, for manganese - up to 1.60 MPC, for nickel - up to 1.35 MPC.

On the section of the Danube 500 m above and 500 m below the city of Vylkove, bottom sediment pollution continues to increase: for copper - up to 3.05 MPC, for manganese - up to 1.70 MPC, for nickel - up to 1.40 MPC.

In the Danube Delta, in the sections of the Ochakiv estuary, the Bystry branch and the Starostamboul branch, the MPC in bottom sediments was exceeded only for copper (by 1.15-2.00 times).

Table 2

Results of the expert assessment of the ecological condition of bottom sediments and ecological risks within the boundaries of the Ukrainian section of the Danube and in the Danube region lakes [14]

Water basin site	Residual HCC quantity (vs MAC)*	Heavy metals content (vs MAC)*	Excess of MAC by pollutants of various hazard categories*			Probability of excessive MACs of various categories pollutants	Assessment of ecological condition of pollutant indicators**	Ecologic risk level***
			1 st hazard category	2 nd hazard category	3 rd hazard category			
<i>Danube – Reni town</i>	II	IV	IV	III	II	0.30	B	considerable
<i>Danube – Izmail town</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Danube – Kiliya town</i>	II	IV	III	III	II	0.40	B	considerable
<i>Danube – Vylkove town</i>	II	IV	III	III	II	0.40	B	considerable
<i>Danube – Ochakiv estuary</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Danube – Bystry estuary</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Starostambulske estuary</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Kagul Lake - vil. Nagirne</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Turka Lake – vil. Orlovka</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Katral Lake – vil. Orlovka</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Kugurlui Lake – branch</i>	II	III	III	II	II	0.30	B	considerable
<i>Yalpug Lake – vil. Kotlovyna (potable water intake)</i>	II	III	III	III	II	0.40	B	considerable
<i>Katlabukh Lake – v. Suvorove</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.30	A	considerable
<i>Lung Lake – vil. Bogate</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Safyan Lake – vil. Safyany</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high

<i>Kitai Lake – vil. Stary Troyany</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.30	B	considerable
<i>Velykui Solonyi liman – nearby vil. Desantne</i>	II	III	I	II	II	0.20	A	high
<i>Sasyk (Kunduk) liman – near vil. Borysivka</i>	II	III	II	II	II	0.30	A	considerable

Remarks:

* ecological condition of the bottom sediments versus to the appropriate MACs and residual quantities of the plant protection chemicals (HCCH) meet: I – “safe”; II – “satisfactory”; III – “medium”; IV – “bad”; V – “very bad”;

** ecological condition of pollution indicators is defined as: “satisfactory” if the indicator $I_{z_{st}} < 3.0$ (A); “unsatisfactory” if the indicator $3.0 < I_{z_{st}} < 3.3$ (B); “bad” if the indicator $I_{z_{st}} > 3.4$ (C);

*** the ecological risk level is defined as “minimum” – at $P_s^c < 0.20$ probability; “high” – at $P_s^c = 0.21–0.37$ probability; “considerable” – at $P_s^c = 0.38–0.63$ probability; “very high” – at $P_s^c = 0.64–0.80$ probability; and “catastrophic” – at $P_s^c > 0.80$ probability.

The analysis of the variability of bottom sediment pollution in the Danube lakes showed that, in general, they meet the established requirements for soil quality. Exceedances of the MPC were detected in only 3.0% of all samples taken in the Kugurluy and Yalpug lakes for three pollutants: lead (1.77 MPC), zinc (1.55 MPC), and copper (2.6 MPC).

Monitoring data on bottom sediment pollution in the Ukrainian section of the Danube and in the Danube lakes are episodic in nature and therefore cannot fully characterize the spatial and temporal variability of bottom sediment pollution [4]. This makes it practically impossible to use statistical models to assess the risk of pollution of these water bodies. In fact, the available data allowed only a preliminary expert assessment of environmental risks.

The assessment of bottom sediment contamination indicates a “satisfactory” condition of bottom soils in areas near the city of Izmail, within the channels of the Ochakivskiy estuary, the Bystryi branch and the Starostambulskiy estuary. For river sections within the cities of Reni, Kiliya and Vylkove, the ecological condition of bottom soils is assessed as “unsatisfactory”.

The level of ecological risk for the entire Ukrainian section of the Danube is estimated in the range of expert assessments of “increased” - “significant”.

In the Danube lakes, the ecological state of bottom sediments is currently assessed as “satisfactory”, with the exception of lakes Kugurluy, Yalpug and Kitay, where the expert assessment determines the level - “unsatisfactory”.

The level of ecological risk of bottom sediment pollution in the Danube lakes is assessed as “increased” (54.5%) - “significant” (45.5%).

When conducting assessment measures to determine the risks of bottom sediment pollution in water bodies of the region, it should be taken into account that bottom sediments are a receiving environment, as well as a secondary source of pollutants present in the aquatic environment. Erosion processes associated with the dynamics of channel flows and wind and wave influences cause high risks of secondary pollution of water bodies.

Conclusions. According to the results of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The integral indicator of the state of land resources $I_{z_{st}}$ within the Danube region has been determined, which varies from 3.00 to 3.16 and corresponds

to the II group of objects, and the qualitative state of land resources is assessed as “unsatisfactory”.

2. The risks of violating the stability of the soil ecosystem have been determined, which in the Artsyz, Kiliya and Tatarbunary districts of the Ukrainian Danube region show a minimum level of risk ($P_s^c = 0.20$). For the Izmail and Reniy districts, the criterion for the level of risk of violating the stability of the soil ecosystem is assessed as “increased” ($P_s^c = 0.25$).

3. The ecological state of soils in the storage areas of the NHZZR in the vast majority of cases corresponds to the assessment of “medium”. The level of ecological risk fluctuates within the limits of “increased” - “significant” ($P_s^c = 0.25–0.40$). However, near the storage warehouses of the National Hydrocarbons and Natural Gas Company in the village of Shevchenkove, Kiliya district, as well as in the village of Zadunaivka, Artsyz district, the highest levels of pollution have been established. The general ecological state of the soils in these places is “severe”, and the level of ecological risk is “high” ($P_s^c = 0.60–0.65$).

4. In the sections of the Danube in the area of the city of Izmail and within the Ochakov estuary, the Bystryi branch and the Starostambul estuary, the values of bottom sediment pollution indicate a “satisfactory” state. However, for river sections within the cities of Reni, Kiliya and Vylkove, the ecological state of bottom sediments is assessed as “unsatisfactory”.

6. The residual amount of chemical plant protection products (DDT, DDE, DDD, γ -HCCH/lindane, heptachlor) in the bottom sediments of the Danube (between the city of Reni and the mouth of the river) and in the Danube lakes in the studied samples was not established (within the sensitivity of laboratory research methods).

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